

General Relativity with the two Galileo satellites DORESA and MILENA

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The Galileo for Science (G4S_2.0) project, funded by the Italian Space Agency (ASI), aims to perform a set of gravitational measurements with the two Galileo satellites GSAT-0201 (Doresa) and GSAT-0202 (Milena) exploiting the relatively high eccentricity of their orbits with respect to that of the other satellites of the Full Operational Capability (FOC) constellation. The elliptic orbit induces a periodic modulation of the on-board atomic clocks frequency with respect to on-ground clocks, the so-called gravitational redshift (GRS). These two satellites have already been used in 2018 by SYRTE [1] and ZARM [2] for a new measurement of the GRS that has improved the previous measurement by Gravity Probe-A [3]. GRS, which is a local position-invariance test, is only one among the predictions of General Relativity (GR) that can be tested with the Galileo constellation. In particular, the main G4S_2.0 goals include, in addition to a new measurement of the GRS, the measurements of the main relativistic precessions of the orbits. Three Italian research institutes are involved: the Center for Space Geodesy (CGS-ASI) in Matera, Istituto di Astrofisica e Planetologia Spaziali (IAPS-INAF) in Roma and Politecnico di Torino (POLITO).

Mathematical framework

The physical-mathematical context on which G4S_2.0 is set up is the one of GR, in the Weak Field and Slow-Motion Limit. This linear approximation can be applied in the case of the Earth as its gravitational field is weak^{§§} and its rotation is not relativistic. In this regime, the metric tensor of spacetime $g_{\mu\nu}$ is treated as the sum of the Minkowski spacetime $\eta_{\mu\nu}$ and a small perturbation $h_{\mu\nu}$, with $|h_{\mu\nu}| \ll 1$. Defining $x^\mu = (ct, \mathbf{x})$ as the coordinates of an inertial frame, G as the gravitational constant, c as the speed of light in the vacuum, $T_{\mu\nu}$ as the stress-energy tensor and $\bar{h}_{\mu\nu} = h_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}\eta_{\mu\nu}h$ with $h = \eta^{\mu\nu}h_{\mu\nu}$, the linearized Einstein's field equations are:

$$\square \bar{h}_{\mu\nu} = -\frac{16\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu}, \quad (1)$$

after imposing the gauge condition $\bar{h}^{\mu\nu}_{;\nu} = 0$. The solution is the so-called "tensor potential" (because of the analogy of equations (1) with Maxwell equations):

$$\bar{h}_{\mu\nu} = 4\frac{G}{c^4} \int \frac{T_{\mu\nu}(ct - |\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|, \mathbf{x}')}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|} d^3x' \quad (2)$$

with

$$\bar{h}^{00} = \frac{4\Phi}{c^2}, \quad \bar{h}^{0i} = -2\frac{A_i}{c^2} \quad (3)$$

where Φ is the Newtonian or gravitoelectric potential and \mathbf{A} is the gravitomagnetic vector potential in terms of the

angular momentum of the system \mathbf{J}

$$\Phi \sim \frac{GM}{|\mathbf{x}|}, \quad \mathbf{A} \sim \frac{G}{c} \frac{\mathbf{J} \times \mathbf{x}}{|\mathbf{x}|^3}. \quad (4)$$

Following this approach, we have a gravitoelectric field produced by masses, analogous to the electric field produced by charges, and a gravitomagnetic field produced by mass currents, analogous to the magnetic field produced by electric currents. These two fields are responsible for two relativistic precessions on a satellite. Given an orbiting object around a non-rotating central mass, GR predicts a precession effect on its orbit. This precession is the so-called Schwarzschild or Einstein precession [4]. If the central mass is rotating, the Lense-Thirring (LT) effect (or "frame dragging") occurs [5]. Another effect must be taken into account, which is the De Sitter precession (or geodetic precession) due to the motion of the Earth-Moon system in the Sun gravitational field [6]. The signature of these relativistic precessions is in the secular effects on the argument of pericenter ω (in the case of Einstein and LT precessions) and on the right ascension of the ascending node, Ω , which is subject to the LT and De Sitter precessions. Measuring these effects is fundamental to study possible deviations from GR as we can compare its prediction with those of alternative theories of gravitation. Moreover, relativistic precessions play a fundamental role in the field of relativistic astrophysics, as in binary systems of pulsars and in active galactic nuclei (AGN).

Implications in the field of Fundamental Physics and Cosmology

An accurate and reliable measurement of Earth gravitomagnetic field can be useful also to investigate the following issues:

- intrinsic gravitomagnetism. It describes the spacetime curvature effects related with mass-energy currents, and not simply the corresponding effects that depend on the motion of a body on a static background field;
- strong field and compact objects. Gravitomagnetism (together with magnetohydrodynamic phenomena) can explain the mechanisms at the basis of the accretion of matter around compact objects and those of acceleration of charged particles with the simultaneous emission of powerful radio jets. Indeed, the relativistic effects, produced by the gravitomagnetic field of the rotating compact object, exert a dragging of the accretion disk and the alignment of the radio jets with the spin of the compact

^{§§} $GM/Rc^2 \ll 1$, where M and R represent, respectively, Earth's mass and radius.

object [7]. Moreover, gravitomagnetism can be useful also to determine the internal structure of neutron stars. From a direct measurement of the angular momentum of a ms-pulsar and consequently of its moment of inertia, the mass-radius relationship can be derived with possible constraint on the equation of state of the neutron star [8].

- Mach's Principle. Mach's idea "inertia here arises from mass-energy there" summarizes very well the meaning of gravitomagnetism. We can interpret the Lense-Thirring effect as a weak GR formulation of the Mach's Principle. Cosmological implications of Mach's Principle are complex and still debated.
- constraints on Dark Matter (DM). Gravitomagnetism measurements can be employed to constrain the presence of DM within our Galaxy. Building a model for the metric tensor including the gravitomagnetic terms [9], it is possible to explain the observed flatness of Milky Way rotation curves.

Furthermore, the Galileo constellation can be employed as a DM detector, with a size of several thousand km, to search for DM candidates, like topological defects. This kind of study was carried out in 2017 [10] by using the GPS constellation. Now, in the G4S_2.0 project, the new challenge is to exploit the higher sensitivity of Galileo atomic clocks.

Methods

A fundamental point in our analysis is to perform an accurate Precise Orbit Determination (POD). This is the procedure for determining the orbit of a satellite with high accuracy by fitting the tracking data with a suitable set of dynamical models for the different effects (including the Non-Gravitational Perturbations (NGPs)). NGPs arise from different sources (the Sun, the Earth and the spacecraft itself) and they are the most difficult to model because of the complex shape of the Galileo satellites and their attitude law. In this context, we want to take a step forward, compared to the state of the art, in the reliability of the dynamical model used for satellites orbits. As a consequence, an enhancement of the NGPs models is required, in particular for the direct solar radiation pressure which is the main one ($\approx 10^{-7}$ m/s²). Our final goal is to build a Finite Element Model of the Galileo FOC spacecraft, as refined as possible. Then, we plan to apply a dedicated Ray-Tracing technique to take into account mutual shadowing effects and multiple reflections. This task will allow us to compute, as accurately as possible, the effect of the interaction of each surface element with the external (or even internal) radiation sources. The corresponding perturbing accelerations will be used in the POD to provide Fundamental Physics measurements

(i.e. GRS, relativistic precessions). As a first step, a 3D-CAD of the satellite has been developed as well as a Box-Wing (BW) model. The BW model simplifies the satellite structure to the central bus (box) and two rectangular solar panels (wing). The geometry and the optical properties provided by ESA's Galileo-Metadata have been used to characterize the satellite surfaces. One of our preliminary POD, in the case of the Galileo GSAT-0208 in nominal orbit, is shown in Figure(1) and compared with a corresponding POD from ESA.

Figure 1: The plot shows our preliminary POD for the GSAT-0208 satellite in nominal orbit with the ESA POD as comparison. Our POD was performed with the software GEODYN (NASA/GSFC) by using only the satellite laser ranging data.

Conclusions

We presented the main goals of G4S_2.0 project related to Gravitation and Cosmology. Both the measurements of the GRS and of relativistic precessions are fundamental to study possible alternative theories of gravitation. Furthermore, the possible presence of DM in the form of topological defects would constitute a significant result in Cosmology. These measurements can be obtained by exploiting, mainly, two Galileo satellites on elliptical orbits and by enhancing the dynamical model at the basis of the POD, improving the NGPs effects estimates.

References

- [1] Delva, P., et al. 2018, in Phys. Rev. Lett., 121, 231101.
- [2] Herrmann, S., et al. 2018, in Phys. Rev. Lett., 121, 231102.
- [3] Vessot, R. F. C., et al. 1980, in Phys. Rev. Lett., 45, 2081.
- [4] Einstein, A., 1916, in Ann. Phys., 354, 769.
- [5] Lense, J., & Thirring, H., 1918, in Zeit. Phys., 19, 156.
- [6] De Sitter, W., 1916, in Mon. Not. R. Astron. Soc., 76, 699.
- [7] Thorne, K. S., et al. 1988, in Near Zero: New Frontiers of Physics, 573-586.
- [8] Kramer, M., et al. 2006, in Science, 314, 97-102.
- [9] Crosta, M., et al. 2020, in Mon. Not. R. Astron. Soc., 496, 2, 2107-2122.
- [10] Roberts, B. M., et al. 2017, in Nat. Commun., 8, 1195.

Short CV

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